

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D7.1

TURNkey Website

<https://earthquake-turnkey.eu/>

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DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

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LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
Uice	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
WPs	Work Packages
JMA	Japan Meteorological Agency
NIED	National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience
USGS	United States Geological Survey
UCB	University of California, Berkeley
ESC	European Seismological Commission
17WCEE	17th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering
ICOSSAR	International Conference on Structural Safety and Reliability
3ECEES	3rd European Conference on Earthquake Engineering and Seismology

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1 INTRODUCTION

The TURNkey website is the main tool to communicate project results and keep the communities and the general public up-to-date with the project progress.

The project website is the first point of access for all interested parties as well as the integral project knowledge base for the consortium members. For this reason, it has both public and private environment: the latter (Intranet) is accessible only to consortium members through apposite credentials.

Both environments of the TURNkey website are briefly described in the following sections.

2 TURNKEY WEBSITE – ACCESS TO PUBLIC

2.1 Home

The TURNkey website has been developed by EUCENTRE and is available at the domain <https://earthquake-turnkey.eu> which allows the direct access to the website homepage (tab *Home*).

At the top of the homepage the user can find both the project logo (on the left) and the different tabs useful for navigating the site (on the right). This part is the same in the other pages of the website.

Subsequently, there is a sequence of photos showing the damages caused by some of the most catastrophic seismic events occurred in the recent years. Below the photos, a brief description of the TURNkey project and its objectives is proposed, followed by the logos of the TURNkey consortium, whose coordinator is NORSAR. Each logo can be clicked on and redirects to the website of the corresponding partner.

At the bottom of the homepage, there is the footer which highlights the website developer (EUCENTRE), the latest news and events and creates the link with the various social networks (i.e., Facebook, Twitter, etc.). Here, there is also the button “Satisfaction Questionnaire” that allows the user to compile a simple satisfaction questionnaire with questions about general user information as well as the structure and the content of the project website. Thanks to this and to Google Analytics, that has been integrated in the portal, it will be possible to understand who and how many will visit the project website and to use this data to track statistics regarding the portal’s traffic, such as the user education level, the work position, the total number of visitors, how long visitors stay on each page, most popular pages, etc. As for the top part, the footer doesn’t change and remains the same in the other pages of the website.

Figure 2.1 shows the website homepage.

(a)

Coordinator

Participants

(b)

(c)

Figure 2.1: TURNkey website homepage: (a) the webpage top, (b) partners' logos and (c) the webpage footer.

2.2 About

After the tab *Home* there is *About* that consists of the following sub-tabs:

- *The project*, that is a section with a general description of the project (see Figure 2.2);
- *The project objectives*, where the project aims are defined in detail (see Figure 2.3);
- *The project work packages*, that is an area with the different buttons related to the work packages (WPs). By clicking each button, the user is redirected to another page where he can be aware of the objectives of the selected button (WP) (see Figure 2.4);
- *The TURNkey consortium*, where there is the map of Europe with the logos of the twenty-one project partners as well as their description, indicating where they come from and what their skills are. Each logo next to the description of each partner can be clicked on and redirects to the website of the corresponding institution (see Figure 2.5);
- *Expert/Advisory group members*, where there is a table indicating the name, the institution and the country of the partners that have agreed to support TURNkey by serving as the Scientific Advisory Board and thereby providing guidance and expertise during the conduct of the project. These experts belong to renown institutions and are leaders in their fields. As shown in Figure 2.6, the supporting members are:
 - Mitsuyuki Hoshiba, Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA);
 - Fumio Yamazaki, National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience (NIED);
 - Paul Earle, United States Geological Survey (USGS);
 - Qingkai Kong, University of California, Berkeley (UCB).

- *Testbeds*, where there is a list of the eight testbeds selected to develop and demonstrate the project results. These testbeds are also georeferenced on the map of Europe. Clicking either on each listed testbed or on its marker on the map of Europe, an area with the corresponding information (e.g., Testbed partner, key stakeholders, existing sensor networks, etc.) will be available (see Figure 2.7).

TURNkey aims to make significant advances in the fields of:

- **Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)** by collecting all available earthquake/hazard related information for the regions of interest (long-term) and by monitoring the regions with the multi-sensor-based earthquake information system (short-term). A critical point is to develop accepted criteria to validate any observed changes and the dissemination of any warnings. Moreover, another critical point will be the translation of the assessed time-dependent hazard into a format that is understandable and useful to the intended end-users of the forecasts. This entails transforming the OEF outputs into statements about risk through close interactions with potential end users and social scientists.
- **Earthquake Early Warning (EEW)** by distributing reliable information that an earthquake is happening as fast and efficiently as possible to all stakeholders hence mitigating earthquake losses. TURNkey will improve existing systems and approaches for estimating the location and intensity of earthquakes, by providing more accurate estimates of imminent earthquake ground motions. This requires increasing the potential of existing crowdsourced systems, developing low-cost multi-sensor instruments that can be deployed in the monitored areas, and advancing current probabilistic methodologies for estimating ground-motion characteristics by propagating the various uncertainties inherent to the problem.
- **Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE)** by informing relevant stakeholders about the most probable damage scenarios. The aim is not only to forecast and issue warnings for main shocks but also for aftershocks. Shake maps will be generated for the areas struck by the earthquake, and the spatial data on the ground-motion parameters will be integrated with vulnerability curves of the building stock to estimate direct and indirect losses. The multi-sensor instruments will monitor fast ground motions (seismic) and also slow movements, e.g. foundation settling and structural creep, using Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) instruments.

Illustration of the chronological sequence of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) and Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE).

TURNkey's purpose is to develop the TURNkey FWCR (Forecasting - Early Warning - Consequence Prediction - Response) platform, a multi-sensor-based earthquake information system, facilitating Earthquake Forecasting and enabling Early Warning and Rapid Response actions, and a versatile and cost-efficient TURNkey multi-sensor unit consisting of seismic (vibration) sensors optimized for EEW and GNSS receivers suitable for various monitoring tasks (structural health monitoring, monitoring of rockfalls, rock/landslides, avalanches, tsunamis) and installation possibilities (free field vs building/infrastructure, field vs urban deployment).

TURNkey will be demonstrated in eight Testbeds: TB-1 to TB-6 refers to European Testbeds, representative of at-risk earthquake-prone areas in Europe, including areas affected by induced seismicity; TB-7 is a Worldwide Testbed; TB-8 represents a mobile European Testbed for aftershocks.

TURNkey's purpose will be attained by exploiting synergies among key actors, exploring data from existing sensor networks, and building on the infrastructure developed in various European TBs, fostering international collaboration, and affiliating with past and ongoing initiatives beneficial for/of interest to the project's success.

Figure 2.2: Sub-tab *The project* of the tab *About*.

The screenshot shows the 'About' tab sub-tab 'The project objectives' on the TURNkey website. The page features a navigation bar with links for Home, About, News & Events, Contact, and Intranet. Below the navigation bar is a header image with the TURNkey logo and the text 'Earthquake-TURNkey / The project objectives'. The main content area is titled 'The project objectives' and contains the following text:

The overall objective of TURNkey is to contribute to earthquake risk reduction, by reducing future economic and social losses in Europe and mitigating the direct and indirect consequences of earthquakes.

The general objectives of TURNkey will be accomplished through the following objectives:

1. To develop and test a new OGF and EEW systems (within the real-time cloud-based TURNkey platform able to integrate and process data during the risk management process) supporting RRS and search-and-rescue (SAR) operations, and to tangibly mitigate the impact of earthquakes on societies, buildings, and infrastructures as well as SAR teams (aftershock forecasting and early warning).
2. To combine existing local/regional information and expert opinion with (1) to provide a robust decisionmaking framework, and its implementation tools, that allows stakeholders to better prepare for and respond to earthquake disasters.
3. To identify the potential technical as well as sociological and socioeconomic barriers (financial, human, organisational and governance) to the implementation of the TURNkey platform, to develop guidelines to address each barrier, and to conduct cost-benefit analyses of the impact of OGF, EEW and RRS measures and compare them to conventional risk reduction measures, starting from the framework of six geographically-based European TBs, one mobile European TB, and one Worldwide TB.
4. To develop training material to raise awareness amongst individuals and public/private organisations of the benefits of the TURNkey platform as well as train them in its use.

The general objectives of TURNkey will be accomplished through the following specific research and Innovation Project Objectives (POs):

PO1: To develop and validate a robust multi-disciplinary (technical, social, economic) research framework that guides the development of EEW, OGF and RRS systems (PO2, PO4 and PO5) and demonstrates how the forecasting and warning systems will improve community resilience to earthquake events across Europe.

PO2: To deploy and improve available instruments for provision of real-time seismic and geodetic data streams, and implement of monitoring and processing steps to be carried out in the six geographically-based, and two non-geographically-based, TBs of TURNkey. The objective will be to test the needs identified and solutions provided in PO1, PO3, PO4 and PO5. The TURNkey platform (PO6) will be implemented in each of the six physical TBs, tested, validated, and feedback provided to make improvements to the system.

PO3: To develop procedures to assess the expected/observed ground motions (ShakeMaps, forecasted and observed) before an earthquake (OGF), during the earthquake but before strong shaking arrives at assets at risk (EEW), and immediately after strong shaking (RRS). These procedures will be implemented within the TURNkey platform (PO6) and applied within the project's TBs (PO2).

PO4: To develop procedures (automatic computer algorithms based on theoretical models and observed data) for the rapid prediction of losses immediately following an earthquake rupture, while accounting for field observations and structural monitoring to update the models. The procedures will generate updated damage and loss predictions by taking into account the procedures for generating theoretical and observation-based ShakeMaps (PO2). The development process will benefit from the TBs actions (PO2) in terms of the physical vulnerability of buildings, functional and systemic vulnerability of systems, monitoring of selected structures and population coverage.

PO5: To develop protocols for response, emergency management, and safety communication - including uncertainties (to technical stakeholders, nontechnical stakeholders, and the public). Based on the decisional rules from Decision Support Systems (DSSs), the goal here is to provide 1) rapid information to emergency decisionmakers about the availability/unavailability of strategic buildings and access areas or the need for people to move to specific emergency areas; 2) rapid information to rescuers about time-dependent seismic risk (for instance, due to aftershocks). A final set of guidelines and protocols for safety communication and response will be prepared to facilitate the practical implementation of the DSSs.

PO6: To integrate the research, innovation and methodologies from the outputs of PO1, PO2, PO3, PO4 and PO5 for the development of the TURNkey multi-sensor unit and the cloud-based TURNkey FWCR platform, which will, for the first time, consolidate currently widely-dispersed tools within a ready-to-deploy system, which is also easily customizable, for a tangible real-time earthquake risk reduction. The sensors of the multi-sensor-based earthquake information system and TURNkey platform will provide multiple possibilities for applications within OGF and EEW as well as for RRS. The overall purpose of the sensors and platform is to serve the public, authorities and stakeholders as a new tangible, cost-effective and easy-to-use tool, which will lead to a significant reduction in uncertainties regarding seismic hazard and structural vulnerabilities.

PO7: To develop best-practice manuals and training materials that, based on stakeholder needs (PO1) and after testing and improvement through the TB implementations, will be used as a "proof-of-concept" of the TURNkey multi-sensor units and TURNkey platform.

Figure 2.3: Sub-tab *The project objectives* of the tab *About*.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.4: (a) Sub-tab *The project work packages* of the tab *About* and (b) an example of the content related to each WP button.

Home | About | News & Events | Contact | Intranet

Earthquake-TURNkey / The TURNkey consortium

The TURNkey consortium

To reach its ambitious objectives, the project has brought together a strong multi-disciplinary team of experts (geophysicists/seismologists, geologists, engineers, disaster risk managers and sociologists) from 21 partner institutions covering 10 EU countries (figure below). These 21 partner institutions with complementary and interdisciplinary competences, comprise: 8 universities (Uice, USt; RWTH, UA, ARL, UNIBQ, UCL, UPe), 7 scientific RTO (EUC, ERGM, KNMI, INFR, NDA, EMSC, CD), and 6 SME specialised in instrumentation (TET, GMP), telecommunication (SIM), database and real-time analysis tools (BBQ, GMR, NOR), and a market research consulting company (NTC).

Coordinator

Stithleian NORSAR

NORSAR was established in 1968 as a joint undertaking between the governments of Norway and the USA. NORSAR is today a private Norwegian research foundation that conducts research, development and advanced advisory work in the fields of seismology, applied geophysics and earthquake engineering and one of the world's largest seismological observatories with more than 65 years of experience with advanced seismological data processing, analysis and parameter extraction in near-real time. NORSAR operates one of the largest seismological networks in Europe and thereby has huge experience in seismic instrumentation, technical laboratory equipment and solutions for data transmission and storage. NORSAR has been a main contributor to the technology presently being implemented at the International Data Centre (IDC) in Vienna for verification of the Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty (CTBT). NORSAR is a registered small medium enterprise (SME).

NORSAR has been conducting research, development and consulting within earthquake hazard and earthquake risk analysis since 1975. More than 120 earthquake hazard and risk related projects have been conducted in Norway and many other countries, including studies for nuclear and hydroelectric power plants, dams, tunnels, waste facilities, offshore platforms and pipelines, petrochemical facilities, as well as design, installation and operation of seismic monitoring networks, with associated earthquake hazard analysis. Since 2004, NORSAR started to widen its competence into earthquake engineering and earthquake risk assessment, thereby creating a multidisciplinary work environment where earth scientists, engineers and IT specialists closely work together on various tasks. NORSAR has a wide experience in the initiation and management of large international research collaboration projects many focusing on earthquake hazard assessment, risk reduction and disaster mitigation studies in developing countries. In the past 25 years, NORSAR has been thereby able to create a worldwide network with researchers, officials and decision makers from educational institutions, academic, governmental bodies and NGOs in almost every part of the world. Of late, the development of innovative technical solutions contributing to a safer society is one of NORSAR's core areas; e.g., conceptualization and installation of near-real-time earthquake loss information systems which establish a major disaster mitigation measure for earthquake prone cities and regions.

Participants

Heiloli Islands

The University of Iceland (Uice), founded in 1911, is a research led state university in Reykjavik, Iceland. Uice offers internationally competitive undergraduate and graduate programs based on the Bologna system. The University employs over 1,500 people and has over 14,000 students, 500 of which are PhD students. The Times Higher Education Supplement ranks Uice at 222 for the top Universities in the world. The Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering (FCEE) at the

Figure 2.5: Sub-tab *The TURNkey consortium* of the tab *About*.

Home | About | News & Events | Contact | Intranet

Earthquake-TURNkey / Expert/Advisory Group Members

Expert/Advisory Group Members

Name	Institution	Country
Mitsuyuki Hoshiba	Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA)	Japan
Fumio Yamazaki	National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience (NIED)	Japan
Paul Earle	United States Geological Survey (USGS)	USA
Qingkai Kong	University of California, Berkeley (UCB)	USA

Figure 2.6: Sub-tab *Expert/Advisory Group Members* of the tab *About*.

Home | About | News & Events | Contact | Intranet

Testbeds

For the purpose of TURNkey's development and demonstration of the results, eight different TestBeds (TBs) are considered: TB-1: Bucharest, Romania; TB-2: Pyrenees, France; TB-3: Towns of Hveragerði and Húsavík (Iceland); TB-4: City of Patras and Aegio region, Greece; TB-5: Ports of Gioia Tauro, Italy; TB-6: Groningen, Netherlands; TB-7: All earthquake affected areas worldwide (virtual TB), and TB-8: EEW system for aftershocks (mobile TB). TBs 1-6 are confined to specific geographic areas in Europe that are exposed to earthquake hazard but have been selected for TURNkey so that cumulatively they provide coverage over a wide range of spatial extents, levels and types of existing monitoring systems, population densities, and types of vulnerable infrastructure. Complementary to these TBs, TB-7 is a non-geographically-based TB, where earthquake effects worldwide are monitored through users of the LastQuake and Earthquake Network apps. Finally, TB-8, which aims at the EEW of aftershocks for the safety of search-and-rescue (SAR) teams, will constitute a localized and mobile solution, to be deployed to any earthquake-struck area where European Urban Search & Rescue (USAR) personnel is required to operate.

- TB-1 – Bucharest, Romania – INFP – (YET, GMP, Ulice, NOR)
- TB-2 – Pyrenees mountain range, France – BRGM (YET, GMP, NOR)
- TB-3 – Hveragerði, South Iceland and Húsavík, North Iceland – Ulice (YET, GMP, SIM, UPat, NOR)
- TB-4 – Patras and Aegio, Greece – NOA, UPat (YET, GMP, BUW, UPat, NOR)
- TB-5 – Maritime ports in Gioia Tauro, Italy – EUC (YET, GMP, NOR)
- TB-6 – Groningen province, Netherlands – Deltares, KNMI – (YET, GMP, EUC, NOR)
- TB-7 – Any earthquake affected area of Europe (even the world) – EMSC, UNIBG
- TB-8 – Mobile EEW for aftershocks Any earthquake-affected area of Europe

(a)

[Home](#) | [About](#) | [News & Events](#) | [Contact](#) | [Intranet](#)

TB-3

Testbed, Partners:
TB-3 – Hveragerði, South Iceland and Húsavík, North Iceland – Ulice (YET, GMP, SIM, UPat, NOR)

Area:
15 km²

Affected population:
4,500

General building stock inventory:
Available

Existing infrastructure:
Roads, bridges, schools, hospitals, harbour, pipelines, boreholes, industrial facilities

Key stakeholders: Municipality of Hveragerði; Municipality of Norðurþing, Húsavík; HSN Health Care Institution of North Iceland, Húsavík; The Icelandic Meteorological Office; Landsvirkjun Energy Company; OR Power; PCC Silicon; ICI Icelandic Catastrophe Insurance Company; National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police; IRCA Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration; RARIK Icelandic State Electricity Providers; Samorka, the federation of energy and utility companies in Iceland.

Existing Sensor networks:
ICEARRAY I (strong-motion, Hveragerði, South Iceland), ICEARRAY II (strong-motion, GNSS-GPS, Húsavík, North Iceland), Icelandic Strong-motion Network, operated by the Earthquake Engineering Research Centre of the University of Iceland; the National Seismic Network (SIL), the GNSS National Network, other geophysical monitoring systems of the Icelandic Meteorological Office.

TB-setting and seismic hazard:
Iceland is the most seismically active region in north-western Europe. The seismic hazard is the highest on two large, complex and populated transform zones, the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ) and the Tjörnes Fracture Zone (TFZ) in the North. The existing infrastructure monitors tectonic and earthquake ground motions, along with structural monitoring of key buildings. The ICEARRAYs comprise the densest urban monitoring systems of earthquake strong-motion in Europe. In addition, ICEARRAY II monitors tectonic motions across the Húsavík-Flatey Fault.

During TURNkey:
A total of 56 TURNkey multisensor units (50 accelerometers and 6 GNSS instruments) will be deployed, thus densifying the free-field urban arrays even further and testing the limits of the TURNkey platform EEW and RRE information in urban areas, and adding structural monitoring systems. The instruments will also be distributed on top of the large faults EEW and RRE purposes. For OEF and EEW purposes, real-time measurements of other geophysical markers (GPS, strain, seismicity etc.) from stations of the other geophysical networks in the region will be made accessible to the TURNkey platform. Additional and existing instruments contributed by Ulice will be deployed in the seismic zones as a part of TB-3 to monitor SISZ seismicity, providing reliable and crucial first P-wave signals for EEW.

Instrumentation

TB-3 – Hveragerði in the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ, left) and Húsavík in the Tjörnes Fracture Zone in the North (TFZ, right). The planned TURNkey instruments, shown in circles: yellow (urban, for EEW) and cyan (rural, EEW and OEF), are either new stations or collocated with existing GPS (squares) and seismic (triangles) stations.

(b)

Figure 2.7: (a) Sub-tab *Testbeds* of the tab *About* and (b) an example of the webpage available by clicking one of the listed testbeds.

2.3 News & Events

The tab *News & Events* will make public all news and events related to the project. At the moment it is possible to view the news about the TURNkey kick-off meeting (and the pictures) and the publication of two articles by the University of Alicante and the local newspaper “Información” describing the TURNkey project and its objectives. The most recent news will also be updated in the website footer. Finally, the idea is that this tab will also consist of other sub-tabs, such as *Publications*, *Marketing and technical material*, *Platform*, etc., all publicly available once the corresponding content will be ready. Figure 2.8 shows tab *News & Events* and an example of the content accessible by clicking one of the available events.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.8: (a) Tab *News & Events* and (b) an example of the content accessible by clicking one of the available events.

2.4 Contact

In this tab the user can ask info about the TURNkey project by writing to the email info@earthquake-turnkey.eu and can subscribe to the TURNkey newsletter by filling in the form (see Figure 2.9).

The screenshot shows the 'Contact' tab of the TURNkey website. At the top left is the TURNkey logo. To its right is a navigation menu with links for Home, About, News & Events, Contact (which is highlighted), and Intranet. Below the navigation is a dark grey breadcrumb trail: Earthquake-TURNkey / Contact. The main content area is split into two columns. The left column has a dark blue background with the heading 'Contact:' and the text: 'For any information and clarifications about the TURNkey project, please write to: info@earthquake-turnkey.eu'. The right column has a blue header 'Subscribe to our newsletter' and a form with three input fields: 'Your Name (required)', 'Your Last Name (required)', and 'Your Email (required)'. Below the form is a blue 'SIGN UP' button.

Figure 2.9: Tab *Contact*.

3 TURNKEY WEBSITE – INTRANET

The tab *Intranet* at the top right of the TURNkey website only allows project members to access the private part of the website through their own username and password.

The activities allowed to members vary by role. More freedom is obviously given to NORSAR and EUCENTRE, as project coordinator and platform administrator, respectively, as well as to each work package leader.

Figure 3.1 shows how to access the intranet environment.

Figure 3.1: (a) Tab *Intranet* on the project website and (b) Intranet login.

Once inside, the Intranet environment is divided into three parts:

- a sidebar on the left containing a series of tabs, the last one of which redirects to the public environment of the TURNkey website;
- a central area, the content of which varies according to the selected tab;
- a right area that allows each user to have an overview of the project members' activities in the platform.

Both left sidebar and right area are pop-ups, just a click on the icons representing the two arrows pointing on the left and right, respectively (see Figure 3.2) is needed to make them appear/disappear.

In the following paragraphs we propose a brief description of the tabs in the left pop-up sidebar.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.2: (a) Left pop-up sidebar and (b) part of the right pop-up area.

3.1 Home

The tab *Home* has a general description of the TURNkey project as show in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Tab *Home*.

3.2 Project Community

After the tab *Home* there is *Project Community* that consists of the following sub-tabs:

- *Members*, where all members that can access the intranet can be viewed;
- *Stakeholders and End-Users*, with a table where the project stakeholders are listed together with the corresponding country, representative, position, email address/website and phone (if available);
- *Blog*, i.e. a virtual area where project members can discuss on the project, its progress, its results, etc.;
- *Activity*, where the activities of each intranet member are listed.

As example, Figure 3.4 shows a part of the content in the sub-tab *Stakeholders and End-Users*.

The screenshot shows a table titled "TURNkey Support Stakeholders.csv" with the following data:

COUNTRY	STAKEHOLDER	REPRESENTATIVE	POSITION	EMAIL/WEBSITE	PHONE
Europe	EPOS	Massimo Cocco	EPOS Coordinator	info@epos-ip.org	
France	LFP Perthus	Petros Papaghiannakis	CEO	info@lfpertus.com	
Greece	Regional Unit Of Achaia	Grigoris Alexopoulos	Head Of Regional Unit Of Achaia	https://www.pde.gov.gr/gr/	
Iceland	Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration	Bergþora Þorkelsdóttir	General Director	vegagerdin@vegagerdin.is	
Italy	Calabria Region	Luigi G. Zinno	Director General	dipartimento.lavoripubblici@pec.regione.calabria.it	

Figure 3.4: Part of the content in the sub-tab *Stakeholders and End-Users* of the tab *Project Community*.

3.3 Project Workplan

The tab *Project Workplan* consists of the following sub-tabs:

- *Work Packages*;
- *Workflow*;
- *Gantt & Milestones*.

In the sub-tab *Work Packages* there is the list of the nine project work packages (WPs): herein the project members can check the progress of each WP and, consequently, of the project itself. By clicking on the title of each WP, a new page with the objectives and the description of the selected WP opens. At the top of this page, there are the title of the selected WP and some buttons that allow the users to do activities (e.g., download files) according also to the role they have in the platform. One of these buttons is “To do”: here the description of each task of the selected WP is available together with the indication of the task lead and the period within which the activity must be carried out (see Figure 3.5).

Finally, the sub-tabs *Workflow* and *Gantt & Milestones* contain the images of the project workflow and the Gantt & Milestones, respectively (see Figure 3.6 and Figure 3.7).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3.5: Example of the content available at the sub-tab *Work Packages* of the tab *Project Workplan*: (a) list of the project WPs, (b) the button “View” and (c) the button “To do”.

TURNkey

WORKFLOW

Figure 3.6: Sub-tab *Workflow* of the tab *Project Workplan*.

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GANTT & MILESTONE

Figure 3.7: Sub-tab *GANTT & Milestone* of the tab *Project Workplan*.

3.4 Project Documents

This tab allows to upload and download the different project documents. In particular, it consists of the following sub-tabs:

- *Deliverables*, where each user can upload and download the project deliverables grouped by work package;
- *Reports*, where each user can upload and download the project reports grouped by work package;
- *Publications*, where each user can upload and download the project publications (e.g., conference papers, etc.);
- *Marketing and technical materials*, where it is possible to upload (for the dissemination leader) and download material, such as flyers, booklet, etc., for the project dissemination;
- *Literature*, where each user can upload and download the papers cited in the deliverables, reports and publications of the TURNkey project.

Figure 3.8 and Figure 3.9 show how the web area corresponding to the sub-tabs *Deliverables* and *Literature*, respectively, are structured.

Figure 3.8: Part of the sub-tab *Deliverables* of the tab *Project Documents*.

Figure 3.9: Sub-tab *Literature* of the tab *Project Documents*.

3.5 Project Products

This tab consists of two sub-tabs, i.e. *Platform* and *Lowcost Multisensor Units*. At the moment these sub-tabs are empty but, when available, their content will concern data on the project platform and the lowcost multisensor units.

3.6 News & Events

Thanks to this tab, the project partners are always aware of the project events, i.e. project and technical meetings, workshops and conferences.

The tab *News & Events* consists of the following sub-tabs:

- *Project Meetings*, where the users with the authority can create such events and upload the corresponding documentation. At the moment, only the sub-tab *TURNkey Kick-off Meeting* contains information about the project kick-off meeting that took place in Oslo, Norway, on June 13 and 14, 2019;
- *Workshops/Technical Meetings*, where the users with the authority can create such events and upload the corresponding documentation (e.g., minutes of periodical technical meetings);
- *Conferences*, that provides a list of past and future conferences related to the project. At the moment there is only the list of the following future conferences:
 - 37th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission (ESC) in 2020 (Corfu, Greece);
 - 17th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering (17WCEE) in 2020 (Sendai, Japan);
 - 13th International Conference on Structural Safety and Reliability (ICOSSAR) in 2021 (Shanghai, China);
 - 3rd European Conference on Earthquake Engineering and Seismology (3ECEES) in 2022 (Bucharest, Romania); it is a joint event of the 17th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering and the 38th General Assembly of the ESC.

Clicking on each conference, it will be possible to upload first the abstract and then the papers accepted for publication in conference proceedings.